

PHYSICAL DEVELOPMENT OF APPLICANTS STUDYING AT EDUCATIONAL CENTERS IN KARSHI CITY

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Abstract. The article presents the results of the study of some anthropometric indicators of 16-18-year-old students studying in educational centres in the city of Karshi. According to him, the average body weight of the examined boys and girls is close to the current standard, and the height is less than the norm, especially in girls. Such a situation calls for further improvement of the promotion of a healthy lifestyle among them.

Key words: educational centre, students, body weight, height, anthropometry, healthy lifestyle.

It is known that physical development refers to the indicators of growth and development of each organism, and it is subject to relevant biological laws. At the same time, indicators of physical development depend on a number of factors, such as children's age, gender, living conditions, nutrition, genetic and individual characteristics. Anthropometric parameters, i.e. height, body mass, chest width, thickness of the subcutaneous fat layer, etc. (somatoscopic and physiometric parameters) are important in examining the level of physical development of children and making appropriate conclusions. Is enough. In this regard, a number of scientific research works are being carried out based on the tasks defined in the laws and decisions adopted by our government. In particular, the results of the research show that the study load, violation of the daily routine, improper diet and other factors have an impact on the health of the students.

As mentioned above, the life of students of the present era, their studies, the breadth of informational material, and the observed environmental imbalance have an impact on the daily lifestyle of students. Therefore, it is important to consider the work of the functional systems of the growing organism when adapting to new conditions. In the study of the physical development of modern students, their modern study, teaching and educational work, neglecting their morphofunctional defects, not only during the study process, but also after acquiring the relevant specialty, causes a number of unpleasant things in their successful work and life.

According to the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations and the World Health Organization, currently more than 840 million people in the world, that is, almost one in eight people, are undernourished, more than 30% of the population of the planet. Is experiencing the problem of not eating enough, lack of the most basic microelements and vitamins. Due to such reasons, more than 160 million children suffer from deficiencies related to height growth, physical and intellectual development.

The body of students differs from the body of adults in terms of metabolism of substances and energy, speed of growth and development processes and other indicators. In addition, adolescence is one of the most important, serious (critical) stages in a person's life.

In this regard, studying the indicators of physical development of students is one of the urgent tasks for physiology and medicine.

Based on the above considerations, during our observations, we studied some anthropometric indicators of 152 entrants aged 16-18 who are being trained in educational centres such as "Ilmu-Ziya", "Magistr Academy" and "Oxford" in Karshi. Tests were conducted using generally accepted methods.

According to the obtained results, the average body weight of the examined boys and girls is close to the current standard, and the length of the body is less than the norm, especially in girls. Among them, 82.7% of boys had normal body weight, 16.1%

less than normal, and 1.2% more than normal. This situation can also be noted in relation to girls.

According to the results of determining the height of the examinees, it can be said that 90.3% of boys have normal height, 8.2% have less than normal height, and 1.5% have medium height. It was noted that it was less than. Also, 26.8% of the examined girls were found to be shorter than the norm.

The muscle strength of the right and left hand of boys is 7.2 and 6.9 kg higher than the norm, respectively. In such girls, instead of the standard 21.9 ± 0.4 and 20.0 ± 0.3 kg, these indicators are 27.5 ± 0.91 and 26.0 ± 0.79 kg, respectively. For example, it shows an increase of 5.6 and 6.0 kg, respectively, compared to the norm.

Based on the above, it can be said that the body mass of boys and girls in the examined groups corresponds to the existing standards, while the height of girls is slightly less than the norm.

In conclusion, it can be said that the body mass, height and arm muscle strength of the students studying in the educational centres of Karshi city do not deviate from the norm. This situation indicates that they are developing normally. The obtained results are not significantly different from the standard level. But this shows that they need to do physical exercises and develop a healthy lifestyle.

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